

A FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS FOR CRACKED PLATES PATCHING WITH SINGLE-SIDED COMPOSITE LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a finite element model for analyzing cracked plates repaired with a single-sided composite patch. The model includes out-of-plane bending effects. The formulation is based on the Reissner-Mindlin plate theory, and an assumed distribution of the transverse shear and normal stresses through the thickness of the plate and patch. The generalized stress-strain relationships are established by using a variational principle. By means of the finite element model present herein, cracked plates patching with single-sided composite laminate can be analyzed with reasonable estimate of the adhesive stresses and the stress intensity factor.

INTRODUCTION

Defects in aircraft structures are known to exist from manufacturing or overload in service. Many of them are hidden and become detectable only when they are sufficiently large in locations conductible to inspection. Aged aircrafts are particularly vulnerable to structure failure by fatigue crack growth. Recent advances in repair technology have made possible to restore the structural integrity of aircrafts that otherwise would be retired. The discipline of fracture mechanics plays a central role in the development of this technology. It is based on the concept of redirecting the load away from the cracked region. A reduction in local stress intensity would prevent the crack from further growth.

Recent advances in adhesive bonding and fiber-reinforced composite materials suggest the possibility of developing more efficient repair techniques. In particular, boron fiber-reinforced plastic (BFRP) patches have had much success in the repair of cracked aircraft components. Several investigators [1-7] have studied the behavior of cracked plates repaired with a patch. Previous methods for analyses of patching crack problems were based on an assumption that the patch and plate are thin. They neglected out-of-plane bending effects in the single-sided crack

patching. However, bending effects will introduce tension in the cracked plate and reduce the efficiency of the patching repair. Obviously, the previous analyses overestimate the load transmitted to the patch and consequently underestimate the stress intensity factor, leading unconservative structural life predictions.

The objective of this study is to develop a finite element model for analyzing cracked plates repaired with a single-sided composite patch. The model includes out-of-plane bending effects. Reissner-Mindlin plate theory will be used to account for variations of the adhesive transverse normal stresses across the plate thickness. The variational principle is applied to determine the generalized stress-strain relationships in the adhesive layer, patch and plate.

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

Consider a composite patch of thickness h_1 bonded to an elastic plate of thickness h_2 by an adhesive layer of thickness h_a as shown in Figure 1. We make the assumption that the transverse shear and normal stresses in the adhesive are constant through the thickness of the adhesive.

Based on the Reissner-Mindlin plate theory, displacement fields of the cracked plate and composite patch are given by

$$\begin{aligned} u_x^{(k)}(x, y, z^{(k)}) &= U_x^{(k)}(x, y) + z^{(k)}\theta_x^{(k)}(x, y) \\ u_y^{(k)}(x, y, z^{(k)}) &= U_y^{(k)}(x, y) + z^{(k)}\theta_y^{(k)}(x, y) \\ u_z^{(k)}(x, y, z^{(k)}) &= U_z^{(k)}(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad , k = 1, 2 \tag{1}$$

where $U_x^{(k)}$, $U_y^{(k)}$ and $U_z^{(k)}$ are the displacement components of a point (x, y) on the mid-plane of the plate or patch, $\theta_x^{(k)}$ and $\theta_y^{(k)}$ are the average rotations of normals to the mid-plane along the xz - and yz -planes, respectively, index k denotes 1 for patch and 2 for plate.

The distributions of the transverse shear and normal stresses through the thickness of cracked plate and patch satisfying the interface stress conditions and equilibrium condition are taken to be

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xz}^{(k)} &= \frac{3Q_x^{(k)}}{2h_k} \left[1 - \left(\frac{2z^{(k)}}{h_k} \right)^2 \right] + \tau_{axz} \left[3 \left(\frac{z^{(k)}}{h_k} \right)^2 + (-1)^k \frac{z^{(k)}}{h_k} - \frac{1}{4} \right] \\ \tau_{yz}^{(k)} &= \frac{3Q_y^{(k)}}{2h_k} \left[1 - \left(\frac{2z^{(k)}}{h_k} \right)^2 \right] + \tau_{ayz} \left[3 \left(\frac{z^{(k)}}{h_k} \right)^2 + (-1)^k \frac{z^{(k)}}{h_k} - \frac{1}{4} \right] \\ \sigma_{zz}^{(k)} &= \frac{\sigma_{azz}}{4} \left[2 + (-1)^k \frac{6z^{(k)}}{h_k} - (-1)^k \left(\frac{2z^{(k)}}{h_k} \right)^3 \right] \end{aligned} \quad , k = 1, 2 \tag{2}$$

where τ_{axz} , τ_{ayz} and σ_{azz} are the adhesive transverse shear and normal stresses, $Q_x^{(k)}$ and $Q_y^{(k)}$ are the transverse shear stress resultants.

The strain-displacement relations for the plate and patch are

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^{(k)} = (u_{i,j}^{(k)} + u_{j,i}^{(k)})/2 \quad , i,j = x, y, z \quad , k = 1, 2 \quad (3)$$

The stress-strain relations for each layer of composite laminated patch are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{C}_{11} & \tilde{C}_{12} & \tilde{C}_{16} \\ \tilde{C}_{12} & \tilde{C}_{22} & \tilde{C}_{26} \\ \tilde{C}_{16} & \tilde{C}_{26} & \tilde{C}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ 2\varepsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{1}{C'_{33}} \begin{Bmatrix} C'_{13} \\ C'_{23} \\ C'_{36} \end{Bmatrix} \sigma_{zz} \quad (4)$$

$$\tilde{C}_{\xi\zeta} = C'_{\xi\zeta} - \frac{C'_{\xi 3} C'_{\zeta 3}}{C'_{33}} \quad , \xi, \zeta = 1, 2, 6 \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C'_{44} & C'_{45} \\ C'_{45} & C'_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 2\varepsilon_{yz} \\ 2\varepsilon_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $C'_{\alpha\beta}$ are the transformed reduced stiffnesses, $\alpha, \beta = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$.

Following assumptions given earlier, the strain-displacement relations in the adhesive become

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{axz} &= [u_x^{(1)}(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2}) - u_x^{(2)}(x, y, \frac{h_2}{2})] / h_a \\ \gamma_{ayz} &= [u_y^{(1)}(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2}) - u_y^{(2)}(x, y, \frac{h_2}{2})] / h_a \\ \varepsilon_{azz} &= [u_z^{(1)}(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2}) - u_z^{(2)}(x, y, \frac{h_2}{2})] / h_a \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where γ_{axz} , γ_{ayz} and ε_{azz} are the adhesive transverse shear and normal strains.

The strain-stress relations in the adhesive are

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{axz} &= K_x \gamma_{axz} \\ \tau_{ayz} &= K_y \gamma_{ayz} \\ \sigma_{azz} &= K_z \varepsilon_{azz} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where K_x , K_y and K_z are the elastic constants of the adhesive.

The development of the generalized stress-strain relations is facilitated by using a variational principle as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \iint_D \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^2 \int_{A^{(k)}} [\delta \varepsilon_{xx}^{(k)} \sigma_{xx}^{(k)} + \delta \varepsilon_{yy}^{(k)} \sigma_{yy}^{(k)} + \delta \varepsilon_{zz}^{(k)} \sigma_{zz}^{(k)} + 2\delta \varepsilon_{xy}^{(k)} \tau_{xy}^{(k)} + 2\delta \varepsilon_{yz}^{(k)} \tau_{yz}^{(k)} + 2\delta \varepsilon_{xz}^{(k)} \tau_{xz}^{(k)} + \delta \tau_{xz}^{(k)} (u_{x,z}^{(k)} + u_{z,x}^{(k)}) - \right. \\ & \left. (C'_{44}{}^{(k)} \tau_{xz}^{(k)} - C'_{45}{}^{(k)} \tau_{yz}^{(k)}) / (C'_{44}{}^{(k)} C'_{55}{}^{(k)} - C'_{45}{}^{(k)} C'_{45}{}^{(k)}) \right\} + \delta \tau_{yz}^{(k)} (u_{y,z}^{(k)} + u_{z,y}^{(k)}) - (C'_{55}{}^{(k)} \tau_{yz}^{(k)} - C'_{45}{}^{(k)} \tau_{xz}^{(k)}) / \\ & (C'_{44}{}^{(k)} C'_{55}{}^{(k)} - C'_{45}{}^{(k)} C'_{45}{}^{(k)}) \right\} dz^{(k)} + \int_{A^{(a)}} [\delta \gamma_{axz} \tau_{axz} + \delta \gamma_{ayz} \tau_{ayz} + \delta \varepsilon_{azz} \sigma_{azz} + \delta \tau_{axz} (\gamma_{axz} - \tau_{axz} / K_x) + \end{aligned}$$

$$\delta \tau_{\alpha\beta} (\gamma_{\alpha\beta} - \tau_{\alpha\beta} / K_{\beta}) dz^{(\alpha)} dx dy$$

$$= \int_{\partial D_T} \left[\sum_{k=1}^2 \int_{A^{(k)}} (\delta u_x^{(k)} T_x^{\nu(k)} + \delta u_y^{(k)} T_y^{\nu(k)}) dz^{(k)} \right] dS \quad (9)$$

where D is the domain of the mid-plane and ∂D_T is the boundary curve with the unit outward normal vector ν . $T_i^{(k)}$ are prescribed tractions along the boundary, and $A^{(k)}$ is the region of the domain.

Substituting Eqns (1)-(8) into Eqn (9) and using Gauss's theorem, one obtains the generalized stress-strain relations.

$$\{\bar{N}\} = [\bar{D}]\{\bar{\epsilon}\} \quad (10)$$

where $\{\bar{N}\}$ and $\{\bar{\epsilon}\}$ are the generalized stress and strain vectors. $[\bar{D}]$ is the corresponding modulus matrix.

$$\{\bar{N}\}^T = \{N_{xx}^{(1)} \quad N_{yy}^{(1)} \quad N_{xy}^{(1)} \quad M_{xx}^{(1)} \quad M_{yy}^{(1)} \quad M_{xy}^{(1)} \quad Q_x^{(1)} \quad Q_y^{(1)} \quad \tau_{\alpha\beta} \quad \tau_{\alpha\beta} \quad \sigma_{\alpha\beta} \quad N_{xx}^{(2)} \quad N_{yy}^{(2)} \quad N_{xy}^{(2)} \quad M_{xx}^{(2)} \quad M_{yy}^{(2)} \quad M_{xy}^{(2)} \quad Q_x^{(2)} \quad Q_y^{(2)}\} \quad (11)$$

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}\}^T = \{U_{xx}^{(1)} \quad U_{yy}^{(1)} \quad U_{x,y}^{(1)} + U_{y,x}^{(1)} \quad \theta_{xx}^{(1)} \quad \theta_{yy}^{(1)} \quad \theta_{x,y}^{(1)} + \theta_{y,x}^{(1)} \quad U_{z,x}^{(1)} + \theta_x^{(1)} \quad U_{z,y}^{(1)} + \theta_y^{(1)} \quad U_x^{(1)} - \frac{h_1}{2}\theta_x^{(1)} - U_x^{(2)} - \frac{h_2}{2}\theta_x^{(2)} \quad U_y^{(1)} - \frac{h_1}{2}\theta_y^{(1)} - U_y^{(2)} - \frac{h_2}{2}\theta_y^{(2)} \quad U_z^{(1)} - U_z^{(2)} \quad U_{xx}^{(2)} \quad U_{yy}^{(2)} \quad U_{x,y}^{(2)} + U_{y,x}^{(2)} \quad \theta_{xx}^{(2)} \quad \theta_{yy}^{(2)} \quad \theta_{x,y}^{(2)} + \theta_{y,x}^{(2)} \quad U_{z,x}^{(2)} + \theta_x^{(2)} \quad U_{z,y}^{(2)} + \theta_y^{(2)}\} \quad (12)$$

The finite element model is established according to the formulation (10). The schematic of isoparametric element is illustrated in Figure 2. The established finite element model in conjunction with standard element and crack tip quarter-point element can be used to analyze repaired structure with single-sided crack patching.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Consider a rectangular plate made of aluminum with dimensions of 635mm × 508mm × 2.286mm, subjected to a uniform far field tensile stress of $\sigma = 1$ MPa. The plate contains a central crack, $2a = 28.1$ mm. The region near the crack is reinforced by bonding a rectangular composite patch 152.4mm × 50.8mm, as illustrated in Figure 3. Four kinds of composite laminate patch with different ply orientation grouping are investigated. The patches are made from an 8-ply boron-epoxy laminate. The laminate moduli of each ply are given as follows:

$$E_{11} = 208.1 \text{GPa}, E_{22} = E_{33} = 35.44 \text{GPa}, G_{12} = G_{13} = 7.24 \text{GPa}, G_{23} = 4.94 \text{GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.1677$$

where the 1-axis is in the fibre direction, the 2-axis is perpendicular to the fibres and the 3-axis is in the thickness direction. The thickness of each ply is 0.127mm. The patch is bonded to the crack plate with an adhesive of thickness 0.1016mm. The Young's modulus of the plate is 71.02 GPa, and the Poisson's ratio is 0.32. The shear modulus and Poisson's ratio of the adhesive are 0.965 GPa and 0.4 respectively.

Table 1 shows the normalized stress intensity factors of cracked plates patched with different ply orientation grouping laminates, in which K_{I_p} and K_{I_u} are the stress intensity factors at mid-surface of the cracked plate with and without reinforcement, respectively. Table 2 shows the normalized adhesive shear stress and normal stress at point A and B with different patch, where the locations of A and B are indicated in Figure 3. Figure 4 shows the deformation of cracked plate and patch with different composite patch.

CONCLUSIONS

A finite element model, which includes the influence of the out-of-plane bending, has been presented for analyzing cracked plates repaired with a single-sided composite patch. The effects of the transverse shear and normal stresses through the thickness of the patch and plate are taken into account. The numerical results reveal that the present model gives a reasonable estimate for the adhesive stresses and the stress intensity factors.

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Table 1. The normalized stress intensity factor with different patches

Patch	K_{lp} / K_{lu}
$[45/-45/45/-45]_S$	0.6549
$[45_4/-45_4]$	0.6900
$[0_4/90_4]$	0.5567
$[0_8]$	0.5038

K_{lp} - The stress intensity factor with reinforcement

K_{lu} - The stress intensity factor without reinforcement

Table 2. The adhesive shear stress and normal stress at point A and B with different patches

Patch	Shear stress (τ_{axz} / σ)		Normal stress (σ_{azz} / σ)	
	A	B	A	B
$[45/-45/45/-45]_S$	0.5596	0.3304	0.2195	-0.1842
$[45_4/-45_4]$	0.5676	0.1879	0.2169	0.0718
$[0_4/90_4]$	0.3620	0.3304	0.2296	0.0940
$[0_8]$	0.3555	0.4156	0.3056	0.1758

Figure 1. Coordinate system for patch, adhesive and plate

Figure 2. Schematic of isoparametric element

Figure 3. Central cracked plate reinforced by rectangular laminate patch

(a). $[45/-45/45/-45]_s$

(b). $[0_4/90_4]$

Figure 4. Deformation of cracked plates and patches